

EFFECT OF MEAN STRESSES ON FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the fatigue behavior of a quasi-isotropic laminate of carbon/epoxy. The derived fatigue life model reasonably well describes the fatigue data obtained by a series of constant amplitude fatigue loading with various mean stress levels ranging from tension to compression. Tensile loading is primarily responsible for developing fatigue damages, whereas compressive loading is negligible.

INTRODUCTION

A great deal of research work has been reported in the literature on fatigue behavior and life prediction of composite materials. Most of these efforts have been restricted to constant amplitude tension-tension cyclic loading for a fixed value of R-ratio (the ratio of minimum to maximum applied fatigue stress). However, a very little amount of work has been reported on the effect of mean stress or R-ratio on the fatigue life.¹⁻² References 1 and 2 show the constant-life diagram based on the limited number of test data.

In this paper a general residual strength model is derived which defines the appropriate relation between fatigue strength and fatigue life accounting for various mean stress levels. The change of the residual strength is based on a degradation rate law similar to the ones proposed by Hahn³ and Yang and Liu.⁴ This model is checked against experimental results obtained by a series of constant amplitude fatigue loading with various mean stress levels ranging from tension to compression. Fatigue damages observed for a few selected specimens are presented in the form of transverse crack, delamination and loss of stiffness as a function of fatigue cycle.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH MODEL

Let $R(n)$ be the residual strength after n cycles and let S_m and S_r be the mean stress and one-half the stress range of the fatigue loading, respectively; that is $S_m = (\sigma_{\max} + \sigma_{\min})/2$ and $S_r = (\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min})/2$ where σ_{\max} and σ_{\min} are the maximum and minimum stress, respectively.

The change of the residual strength $R(n)$ at n cycle is assumed to be

$$\frac{dR(n)}{dn} = -f(S_m, S_r)/CR(n)^{C-1} \dots \quad (1)$$

where C is material parameter and f is assumed to be a function of S_m and S_r only. Integration of Eq (1) from 0 to n leads to

$$R^C(n) = R^C(0) - f(S_m, S_r) \cdot n \dots \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) shows the relationship between the static strength $R(0)$ and residual strength $R(n)$ through a parameter C and a function $f(S_m, S_r)$.

The statistical distribution of the ultimate strength $R(0)$ is assumed to follow the two-parameter Weibull distribution, i.e.

$$F_{R(0)}(X) = P_r\{R(0) \leq x\} = 1 - \exp[-(\frac{X}{\beta})^\alpha] \dots \quad (3)$$

where α is the shape parameter and β is the scale parameter.

Let N be the fatigue life, and then the condition of fatigue failure is

$$R(n) = \bar{\sigma} \text{ whenever } N = n \quad (4)$$

where

$$\bar{\sigma} = \begin{cases} \sigma_{\max} & \text{if } \sigma_{\max} > |\sigma_{\min}| \\ \sigma_{\min} & \text{if } |\sigma_{\min}| > \sigma_{\max} \end{cases}$$

From Eqs (2) and (4)

$$N = [R^C(0) - \bar{\sigma}^C]/f(S_m, S_r) \dots \quad (5)$$

If the ratio of $\bar{\sigma}$ to the characteristic static strength is such that $(\bar{\sigma}/\beta)^C \ll 1$, the distribution of fatigue life N is approximated by eqs (3) and (5)

$$F_N(n) \approx 1 - \exp\left\{-\left[\frac{n}{\beta^C/f(S_m, S_r)}\right]^{\alpha/c}\right\} \dots \quad (6)$$

The above distribution of the fatigue life is a two parameter Weibull distribution with the shape parameter α/c and the characteristic fatigue life (scale parameter), $\beta^C/f(S_m, S_r) = N$.

If the fatigue life in a variety of mean stress levels holds the following empirical relationship

$$S_r = K |A - S_m|^{dN^b} \dots \quad (7)$$

where K , A , d , b are the model parameters, we obtain

$$f(S_m, S_r) = \beta^C \left\{ \frac{K|A - S_m|^d}{S_r} \right\}^{1/b} \dots \quad (8)$$

From eqs (2) and (8), we obtain

$$R(0) = \left[R^C(n) + \beta^C \left(\frac{K|A - S_m|^d}{S_r} \right)^{1/b} \cdot n \right]^{1/c} \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) represents the residual strength model under constant amplitude fatigue for a variety of mean stress levels.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system used in this paper was T300/934 graphite/epoxy supplied in prepreg form by Fiberite Corporation. Panels of a quasi-isotropic laminate $[0/45/90/-45]_{2S}$ were fabricated in an autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The fiber volume content was determined to be 66 percent. Straight-sided coupon specimens with end tabs attached were cut from the panels using a diamond-impregnated saw. All specimens were 20 mm wide and 70 mm long in test section.

Specimens were subjected to a sinusoidal fatigue stress with 10 Hz of frequency considering mean stress levels, 0, 69, 138, 207, 293, 345, -69, -138, -207 and -293 MPa. Four different stress amplitudes were employed at each mean stress level to obtain life data for construction of S_r -N. Fatigue test was terminated at either fatigue failure or 5×10^6 cycles. Four to nine replications were tested. In the tension-compression and compression-compression fatigue all specimens were tested using a side support device to prevent specimen buckling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Fatigue Life

The results of static tensile and compressive strength are summarized in Table 1, with Weibull parameters estimated by the maximum likelihood method.

Table 1 Static strength

	Weibull Parameter		
	Mean, MPa	Shape, α_s	Scale, β_s
Tension	528	17.8	545
Compression	512	21.6	524

The fatigue shape parameter $\hat{\alpha}_f$ and scale parameter (characteristic (fatigue) life) \hat{N} were estimated by employing a statistical method similar to a procedure described elsewhere.⁵ The average value of $\hat{\alpha}_f$ over different S_m is computed as follows: $\hat{\alpha}_f = 1.731$ for positive S_m and 1.421 for negative S_m . Using the shape parameters for static and fatigue loading, the parameter c was found to be 10.28 for positive mean and 13.2 for negative mean.

The A, b, d, and K were estimated by least square fitting of Eq (7) using the fatigue life data and are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Model parameters

	A	c	b	d	K
Positive Mean	545	10.28	-0.081	0.869	3.083
Negative Mean	524	13.20	-0.081	0.746	6.333

Figs. 1 and 2 show the characteristic fatigue lives vs. S_r for positive and negative mean stress, respectively. The various symbols represent the fatigue lives obtained experimentally, and the solid line is obtained from Eq (7). With a few exceptions, the fitting of fatigue life data to Eq (7) is excellent for various mean stress levels ranging from negative mean to positive mean.

For checking the validity of the residual strength model, fatigue life and residual strength were converted to static strength using Eq (9). Figs. 3 to 5 show the distribution of the converted static strength from fatigue life data for $S_m = 0, -138,$ and 138 MPa. The solid line is static strength distribution obtained by using the parameters in Table 1. Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the converted static strength from residual strength data using Eq (9). The correlation is reasonable in view of the scatter of composite strengths.

2. Fatigue Damage

The damages incurred during fatiguing have been assessed in the form of transverse crack, delamination, and loss of modulus. The damage study was made under two

Fig. 1. S_r - N curves for positive mean stresses.

Fig. 2. S_r - N curves for zero and negative stresses.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the converted static strength from fatigue life data for $S_m = 0$.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the converted static strength from fatigue life data for $S_m = -140$ MPa.

Fig. 5. Distribution of the converted static strength from fatigue life data for $S_m = 140$ MPa.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the converted static strength from residual strength data.

fatigue loadings: $\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = 38/380$ and $-380/-38$. Fig. 7 presents a typical crack density vs. fatigue cycle. The crack density increases rapidly in the early stage of fatigue life and remains nearly unchanged for the rest of the fatigue life for all specimens. Fig. 8 shows the x-ray pictures of typical specimens fatigued up to the cycles indicated. An extensive delamination occurs in tension-tension fatigue. This laminate does not show any delamination under static loading. In compression-compression fatigue, no transverse crack and delamination were observed except for the unsupported small area in some cases.

Fig. 7. Crack density vs. fatigue cycle for $\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = 38/380$ MPa.

(a) $\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = 38/380$ MPa

(b) $\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = -380/-38$ MPa

Fig. 8. X-ray showing the delamination incurred at 10^5 cycles.

The change of modulus as a function of fatigue cycle was measured by an extensometer with one inch gage length. Fig. 9 presents the E_n/E_0 vs. number of fatigue cycles, where E_n and E_0 are the longitudinal modulus at number of cycles and prior to fatigue, respectively. In most cases the modulus decreases rapidly in the early stage of fatigue life and thereafter decreases rather moderately as a function of fatigue cycle. The rapid decrease of modulus in the initial stage appears to be

Fig. 9. E_n/E_0 vs. fatigue cycle for $\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max} = 38/380$ MPa.

somewhat related with the transverse crack density. The degree of change in modulus is different from specimen to specimen, as well as the fatigue stress level. In compression-compression fatigue, the modulus practically remains unchanged until the last measurement which is equivalent to more than 80 percent of the fatigue life. Thus, the transverse cracks and delamination appear to be mainly responsible for the degradation of stiffness.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The fatigue model from the regression analysis describes adequately S_r -N relation for various mean stress levels. The model parameters in tension are slightly different from those in compression.
2. The residual strength model describes fairly well the converted static strength distribution from both residual strength and fatigue life data.
3. Tensile loading is primarily responsible for fatigue damage processes in this laminate, whereas the damage under compressive fatigue loading is negligible.

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